

Experienced Social Segregation in Fifteen Minute Cities: A Data and Modeling Approach

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Abstract The Fifteen Minute City (15MC), as a planning concept, is often praised as a tool that can be used to improved urban quality of life. However, it has received many criticisms regarding how its application may increase or exacerbate existing urban segregation. In this work, our objective is to expand the existing literature on the topic and analyze how travel behaviours, aligned with the 15MC concept, may increase experienced segregation in cities, especially for underprivileged groups. To achieve this, we intend on simulating a population that stays within a 15-minute distance of their neighborhood whenever physically possible. By modeling a travel behaviour that is not necessarily realistic, but instead illustrates the implications of living within a 15MC, we aim to highlight the shortcomings of this concept in addressing income inequality and social segregation in contemporary cities.

1 Introduction

The Fifteen Minute City (15MC) is an urban planning concept initially proposed by urbanist Carlos Moreno [1] in 2016. Introduced with the goal of decreasing contemporary cities' dependence on cars, it gained new notoriety after the COVID-19 pandemic, and has been applied in multiple cities around the globe to various degrees of success [2].

The 15MC is based primarily on the idea that every resident of a city should be able to fulfill all or most of their basic needs – defined as living, working, commerce, healthcare, entertainment, and education – within a radius of 15 minutes by foot or bicycle of their home, incentivizing a decentralization of urban services.

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Published in "Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Location Based Services (LBS 2025)", edited by Juha Oksanen, Henrikki Tenkanen, Pyry Kettunen and Ville Mäkinen, LBS 2025 7-9 May 2025 Otaniemi, Espoo, Finland.

This contribution underwent double-blind peer review based on the paper.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15352651>
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However, one of the main criticisms of the 15MC refers to its role in accentuating urban segregation. The basic idea of a complete neighborhood in which individuals may resolve all of their needs in itself can be dangerous to integration within a metropolis, an idea explored in *The 15-minute city quantified using human mobility data* [3], which serves as the main inspiration for this work. In it, the authors explore the correlation of a population's access to and usage of services within 15 minute walking distance on experienced segregation, and find that in neighborhoods that more closely resemble the 15MC model, individuals of higher income levels found themselves to be less segregated from others, but the inverse was true for those of lower income.

To build on these previous findings, we aim to model trips as if every individual maximized the use of services within 15 minutes as much as possible and again analyze experienced segregation in this scenario. By taking this behaviour to its logical extreme, we observe what would actually happen to a population living in the way proposed by the 15MC concept. Through this, we hope to gain further insights into this planning paradigm's effect on urban living. We aim to determine whether its potential benefits in fact outweigh these observed negatives, and if the latter can be mitigated through intelligent planning and development.

2 Data and Methodology

2.1 Data Sources and Limitations

The main datasets to be used in this work are:

- Mobile phone location data from SafeGraph, containing anonymized and aggregated mobility traces from all major urban areas in the United States from the year 2021, which has been demonstrated to be representative of the general population [4].
- A simulated dataset, intended to demonstrate the consequences of extreme adherence to the 15MC ideal, to be generated based on the original dataset as described in section 2.3.

The original dataset contains, for each "point of interest" (POI), its location and NAICS code (a classification of businesses used by the U.S. federal government), as well as the number of visits it received from each Census Block Group (CBG, the smallest statistical unit with data available in the U.S. census, containing 600-3,000 people) within a given timeframe. We assume that each individual trip originates from the population-weighted centroid of the CBG, with median income values used for each CBG.

Additional data on population, income, and CBG geometry is sourced from the U.S. Census, and street data for walkability is obtained from OpenStreetMap. Travel times are calculated using the `r5py` library [5].

2.2 Data Analysis

The analysis of both datasets revolves around three main metrics, all introduced and explored at length in ref. [3]:

- 15-minute Access: obtained by counting the amount of POIs in 15-minute walking distance of a given neighborhood's (CBG) centroid, obtaining the percentile rank of each neighborhood within its urban area for each category, and averaging the categories weighed by the proportion of trips made to amenities of that category throughout the entire dataset.
- 15-minute Usage: defined as the proportion of trips taken by residents of a given neighborhood to POIs within 15-minute walking distance.
- Experienced Segregation: each individual receives a value for each POI they visit equal to the average difference in income ranks between them and other individuals that visited the same POI, weighed by the population of each rank at that POI. This is aggregated to the CBG level by averaging over all POIs, weighed by the number of visits from the CBG to said POI, and finally inverted to obtain the segregation value.

The term "Experienced Segregation" is then, in essence, a measure of exposure, using the individual's spatial and temporal coexistence with others of different neighborhoods as a proxy for interactions between them. While this practice is generally accepted in the literature [6], we recognize that it is not perfect: one might find, for example, that POIs with low-wage workers and an affluent clientele would appear to possess a low experienced segregation score, even though such an environment is not very conducive to meaningful interactions. Still, we consider this as a reliable enough proxy for interactions for our purposes.

To elaborate our analysis, we plan on exploring not only the previously mentioned variables, but also other forms of measuring experienced segregation, such as the racial segregation index proposed by Athey et al. [7].

2.3 Modeling

Our main objective is to analyze the same variables in the original dataset as well as under modeled behaviour, in order to explore the effects of maximizing 15-minute usage as much as possible within a certain population. To achieve this, we plan on doing the following:

1. For every trip taken over to a POI that is not within the 15-minute threshold for that neighborhood, replace it with a trip to a POI of the same category within said threshold, choosing randomly from among possible options in a uniform distribution.
2. Repeat the simulation for multiple iterations and take the average between them for all variables of interest.

This is, evidently, not reasonable behaviour for an actual population. However, the goal is not to make a projection of actual behaviour, but to explore the logical consequences of the idea of the 15-minute City when taken to its extreme, minimizing trips outside of individuals' 15-minute area while keeping current constraints on services.

Having a harsh cutoff on the 15-minute number is a conscious choice; this is a mostly arbitrary number chosen to draw the line on what distance is acceptable for an individual to traverse to perform their daily tasks, as can be seen by the existence of many other planning paradigms that use 10 or 20 minutes instead. [8]

3 Expected Results

Initially, we expect to see confirmation of trends already observed currently in the literature [3] regarding the 15-minutes concept, mainly:

- A positive correlation between usage and segregation for lower-income residents;
- A negative correlation between the same variables for higher-income residents.

We also expect to see similar trends when looking at other segregation measures, including racial segregation, as those are highly correlated to the measure of experienced segregation by income already presented. Additionally, we also plan to evaluate how much each neighborhood changes between our real and simulated datasets, and what relationships that has to our other variables.

Through this, we hope to demonstrate that the 15-minute city is an idea that lends itself to segregating cities in an unequal manner, keeping lower income residents from interacting with those outside of their socioeconomic group. The implementation of such an urban planning paradigm needs to be carefully considered by governments and lawmakers, since the indiscriminate application of its propositions may lead to further reinforcing historical inequalities already at play in the worlds' cities.

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